

**EFFICACY OF AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT IN DARK CIRCLES – A
CASE STUDY****Dr. Simran Kamtekar^{1*}, Dr. Kailas Sonmankar², Dr. Sachin Hajare³, Dr. Udit
Dhaygude⁴**

^{*1}PG Scholar, ²Associate Professor, ³PG Scholar, ⁴Assistant Professor,
Department of Kriya Sharir RAPMC.

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Corresponding Author*Dr. Simran Kamtekar**

PG Scholar, Department of Kriya
Sharir RAPMC.

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ABSTRACT

The skin is not only the body's largest organ but also a major determinant of external appearance, playing a central role in cosmetic health and aesthetics. As the most visible part of the body, the skin reflects one's age, lifestyle, and overall well-being. Even minor skin concerns such as pigmentation, acne, dullness, or premature aging-can significantly impact self-confidence and emotional well-being. One of the common worrying factors related to skin is Dark circles. It affects almost all age groups and is most commonly related to stress and anxiety. One of the common complaints in dermatology is the presence of dark circles. This study is aimed to evaluate the ayurvedic management in dark circle.

KEYWORDS: Dark circles.**INTRODUCTION**

Dark circles comes under the broad umbrella of features of aggravation of Vata like blackish discoloration (Karshnya), Dark colouration (Shyavata), which can also be categorized under disease predominant in Vata (Vata Nanatmaja Vikara). In spite of its prevalence and cosmetic importance, there are very few reported works regarding dark circles.^[1]

Vyanga is explained as a Kshudra Roga in Ayurveda. The etiological factors of Vyanga, psychological factors like Krodha (anger), Shoka (grief) and Shrama (exhaustion), which are commonly found in most of the patients.

In Samprapti of Vyanga, Acharya Charaka has mentioned that the aggravation of Pitta along with Rakta is the chief culprit for initiation of the pathology. Vyanga is a Rakta Pradoshaja Vyadhi,^[2] hence the very first Dosha affected is Rakta Dhatu. Dosha Prakopaka Hetus like Krodha, Shoka and Shrama are mainly Tama (Manasika Dosha), Pitta and Vata (Shareerika Dosha) dominance,^[3] vitiates the Agni (Pitta Dosha) which resides in Rasa and initiates the pathogenesis of Vyanga.

lakshanas of dark circles can be correlated with Vyanga lakshana like Niruja, Tanu, and Shava Varna Mandalas. Hetu of dark circles are: excess intake of Katu, Tikta, Kashaya, Amla, Lavana Rasatmaka Ahara, Abhishyandi Ahara Sewana, Usna, Tiksha Ahara Sewana, Vihara: stress and Diwaswapa, Ati krodha, Ati shoka, Ati bhaya (Manasika hetu).^[4]

Dark circles, also known as periorbital hyperpigmentation, are a common cosmetic concern characterized by discoloration of the skin beneath the eyes. Various factors such as lack of sleep, dehydration, poor nutrition, sun exposure, and underlying health conditions can contribute to their development. Effective management often involves a combination of lifestyle modifications, skincare, and in some cases, medical or cosmetic treatments.

CASE REPORT

Name: XYZ

Age: 44 yrs

Gender: female

Residence: Mumbai

History of present illness

CASE DISCUSSION

A 44 year old married female of pitta vata prakruti patient came to the OPD with c/o dark circle since 4-5 years. There was no any sign of inflammatory pigmentation or Ruja present.

History of past illness – NAD

No any addiction.

Past H/o: No any such history found.

Past surgical history: No any relevant surgical history.

Family history: No any family members having same complaint.

Personal History

Occupation- Housewife

Ahar – Mixed diet (Veg and non veg), taking meal 3 times/day, guru snigdha abhishyandi ahar, bakery products.

Vihara – Diwaswap.

Nidra – Samyak

Agni- Mandagni

On Examination: Vital signs.

Pulse: 80/min

BP: 130/80 mmHg

Systemic examination

R.S: B/L Symmetrical, clear

CVS: S1, S2 heard, no any added sounds

CNS: Conscious well oriented

GIT: Bowel movement- Regular, tongue- Coated

P/A: Non tender, soft

Astavidha pariksha

Naadi: 80/min

Mala: Prakrut 1 times/day

Mutra: Prakrut 4-5 times/day

Jihva: Sama

Sparsha: Ushna and Ruksha

Shabda: Prakruta

Akruti: Madhyama

Druk : Samyak

Samprapthi Ghataka^[5]

Dosha: vata pitta

Dushya: rasa rakta

Agni: vishamagni

Agni Dushti: Mandagni

Srotas: Rasavaha raktavaha

Srotodushti: Sanga

Adhishthana: akshikuta Twak

Vyadhimarga: Bahya

Sanchara sthana: Twak

Sadhyasadhyatva: Sadhya

MATERIALS AND METHODS

After assessment and examination patient was initially administered Ampachak vati for deepan and pachan, followed by the subsequent line of treatment.

Table No 1: Shaman aushadhi chikitsa (Abhyanatar).

Sr no	Aushadhi	Dose	Anupana	Duration	Effect
1	Ampachak vati	250mg twice a day	Warm water	Before meal	Deepan Pachan
2	Sarivadyasav + Mahamanjishthadi kashay	10ml each Twice a day	Warm water (20 ml)	After meal	Raktaprasadan Raktashodhan Pittashaman
3	Varnya gana churna	Half tea spoon Twice a day	Warm water (half cup)	After meal	raktaprasadan

Table no 2. Shaman aushadhi chikitsa (Bahya)

Sr no	Aushadhi	Duration	Effect
1	Yashti churna lepa	Once at morning	Varnya
2	Prasarini tail for LA	Once at bed time	Raktaprasadak

Pathya and apathya were advised to the patient during the course of treatment.

Pathya – Naatisnigdha ahar, Laghu ahar, Anaabhishtyandi, Ushna ahar

Apathya – Avoid curd, bakery products, maida, cold drinks, heavy food, vidagdha amla food

Duration of treatment – 1 month

Follow up – After 7 days

Observation and result-

After shaman chikitsa the darkness of circle was gradually becoming normal.

1st follow up – It was observed that the dark circles were slightly reduced. Digestion also started to improve.

3rd follow up – The dark circles were significantly reduced. Digestion improved, so appetite also increased.

4th follow up- Dark circles completely reduced

The gradations of changes in colour are mentioned in below chart.

Symptom	1 st follow up	2 nd follow up	3 rd Follow up	4 th Follow up
Shyvata	+++	++	+	-
Mandagni	+++	+	-	-

Day 1 2nd follow up 4th follow up

DISCUSSION

According to Ayurveda, due to anger and physical exertion, Vata gets aggravated and combines with Pitta. Suddenly, it moves towards the face and manifests in the facial region. It results in the formation of a painless, thin, and dark bluish (or brownish) discoloration on the face, which is termed as “Vyang”^[6]

Dark circles can affect individuals of all ages and are often associated with fatigue, stress, aging, and genetic predisposition. While not medically harmful, dark circles can significantly impact a person’s appearance and self-esteem. In Ayurveda, dark circles are viewed not merely as a cosmetic issue but as a sign of internal imbalance, requiring a holistic approach to the mind, body, and doshas.

Mode of action of drug

1. Mahamanjishthadi kashay

The ingredients of Mahamanjishthadi Kashaya are mentioned in Kandughna, Varnya, Deepaniya, Dahaprashamana and Vayasthapana mahakashaya.^[7] All the drugs in this medicine are of Tikta and Kashaya rasa. So, Ama pachana, Agnidipana, kleda Shoshana, pitta and Kapha Shamana was expected so that Rakta Prasadana action is effectively carried out.

2. Sarivadyasava

It is used in the treatment of various skin disorders and urinary diseases. It is having actions like Raktashodhska, sheetavirya, urinary antiseptic, dipana, pachana, and antistress effects.

3. Yashti churna**4. prasarini tail****CONCLUSION**

As the case demonstrate marked relief in discolouration, it can be concluded that this treatment is both effective and safe. Pathy role plays an important role in the treatment. Results observed in this case encouraging and emphasize the importance of ayurvedic intervention in the successful management of dark circles.

REFERENCES

1. Ankita P, Shivkumar Harti, Mangalagowri Rao - Study to Know the Impact of Ayurvedic Lifestyle on Dark Circles Around Eyes. Current Traditional Medicine, December 2020.
2. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala, Charaka Samhita, Sutra sthana. Vaidya Jadhavaji Trikamji Aacharya., editor. Vividashitapeeteeya Adhyaya 28/11-12. Chaukhamba Prakashan, Varanasi, 2009; 179. Reprint ed.
3. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala, Charaka Samhita, Sutra sthana. Vaidya Jadhavaji Trikamji Aacharya., editor. Vividashitapeeteeya Adhyaya 28/11-12. Chaukhamba Prakashan, Varanasi, 2009; 179. Reprint ed.
4. Pranita Milind Deshpande, Anil Managuli - ROLE OF NASYA WITH KUMKUMADI TAILA IN IMPROVING DARK CIRCLES - A CASE STUDY. International Ayurvedic Medical Journal, India, August 2020.
5. Kaur Manpreet, Sharma Anita, Khatik Rohit Kumar, Meena H. M.- THE ROLE OF AYURVEDA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF VYANG W.S.R. TO MELASMA. AYUSHDHARA, March- April 2016; 3(2).
6. Kaviraj Ambikadatta Shastri, editor. Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi. 14th ed. 2003. Sushruta. Sushruta Samhita, Nidana Sthana, Kshudraroga Nidana Adhyaya, 13/45-46; p. 288.
7. Sharma R.K, Dash Bhagwan, Agnivesa's Charak Samhita, Sutra Sthan, Vol. 5, Chapter-4, reprint 2015, Varanasi, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series office, 2015.